

State of the Art and Trends of the Research on Women, Entrepreneurship and Success: A Bibliometric Review

Nor Syahida Mohamed

Faculty of Applied and Human Sciences, Universiti Malaysia Perlis, Malaysia.

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online 02 February 2022	In the last few decades, the rise of women's entrepreneurship topic attracts considerable attention among scholarly research. Hence, women's interest in business witnessed a rapid growth that made them reach the strength to impact the global economy. Owing to the rising quantity of studies in this area, this paper analyses and reports on various sorts of published works concerning women's entrepreneurship success. Thus, this study employs bibliometric analysis based on the data from the Scopus online database as of January 2022. The study targeted 300 valid documents for further analysis based on the search results for 'key terms.' The author then used VOS viewer to visualise data. This paper presents the findings from typical bibliometric indicators, focusing on the rate of publication growth, citation analysis, and research productivity. According to the results, there has been a rise in women entrepreneurs' success literature growth rate since 1988. An analysis by country, The United States of America ranks top in productivity with 68 (22.67%) published documents. Concerning the frequency of citations, Buttner and Moore (1997)'s article emerges as the most cited article with an average of 19 citations per year. Overall, the increased number of works on women's entrepreneurship success indicates growing awareness of its importance and specific requirements text.
Corresponding Author Nor Syahida Mohamed https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5785-7254	
KEYWORDS: Women, Entrepreneurship, Success, Bibliometric Analysis, Science Production, Scopus Database	

I. INTRODUCTION

Women's entrepreneurship is defined as a "woman or a group of women who initiate, organise and run a business concern." In the last few decades, women entrepreneurship topic attracted considerable attention among scholarly research (Crecente, Sarabia & Val, 2021). Hence women's interest in business witnessed a rapid growth that made them reach strength to impact the global economy. Policymakers and researchers view it as a potential means of achieving economic development and social development (Crecente et al., 2021). Besides, it is also recognised as a source of increasing entrepreneurial diversity in a range of economic contexts (Costa & Pita, 2020).

Furthermore, the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor women's entrepreneurship report 2018/2019 estimated that nearly 231 million women were initiating or running new ventures worldwide in 2019 (Elam et al., 2019). With this trend, there has been an increasing number of studies on female entrepreneurship, which offers a valuable focus for concerted scholarly research. Accordingly, Examining the nature and dynamics of published articles is a common technique among scholars who work in the fields of bibliography and

bibliometrics. As able to track the evolution of the observed topic of interest (Roth et al., 2020), or journal publication activity or scientific discipline (Ahmi, Tapa & Hamzah, 2020). Pritchard (1969). defined bibliometric as "the application of statistical and mathematical methods to books and other media of communication." A bibliometric study is commonly used to evaluate the quantity and quality of published documents to identify patterns in a specific research topic.

Moreover, bibliographic databases like Scopus have advanced analytic tools to empower scholars to exploit the potential of accessible bibliographical data fully. Thus, according to Zakaria et al. (2020), the most common indicators detected employing bibliometric analysis are publication classification, citations, authorship, publication impact, and country. Nonetheless, the bibliometric methodology is often divided into two forms of analysis: performance analysis and science mapping (Ahmi et al., 2020), evaluated through the number of citations or citations per year, total h-index or g-index, cite score and some of the other various matrices. The first deals with the productivity of individuals, institutions, and nations and the second deals

with the prevalent themes in a scientific field. In other words, the ability to analyse the development, trend, or productivity of publications by evaluating the quantity of publications in a specific research area. In addition to the contextual narrative, current publications have emphasised the significance of women’s entrepreneurship in the context of economic rehabilitation (Aparicio et al., 2022) and domestic economy strengthening (Wach et al., 2016). as a driver of entrepreneurial success, women empowerment (Agarwal et al., 2021) or a trigger of future entrepreneurial intentions (Armuña et al., 2020).

Consequently, through multidisciplinary approaches towards the issues of “women”, “*entrepreneurship*”, and “*success*”, The academic community’s interest in interpreting these phenomena from the perspectives of various scientific areas has grown as a result of research activities. The continuous expansion in the quantity of research articles recognises the need to approach the analysis of such publications from the standpoint of bibliographic analysis as an effective means of interpreting the current literary corpus. Bibliographic studies of scientific works dealing with concerns of women’s involvement have been observed in the field of psychology (Gruber et al., 2021), management (Majumder et al., 2021), and higher education (Slavinski et al., 2020). However, despite the rise of articles examining the phenomena of “*women entrepreneurship*” noted within the previous years, there is a scarce bibliographic paper covering topics such as women entrepreneurship success, sustainable women entrepreneurship, or women entrepreneurship performance. Given that recently the publication of bibliographic papers from the position of gendered publication trends (Kataria, Kumar & Pandey., 2021) or gender inequality in scientific careers has become especially topical (Majumder et al., 2021). Thus, to fill these gaps, we intended to answer the following questions in this study:

- ❖ Q1: What is the current publication trend in women entrepreneurship success?
- ❖ Q2. What are the cooperation networks among various countries, journals and individuals in the Women entrepreneurship success field?
- ❖ Q3: Which are the most influential articles on women entrepreneurship success?
- ❖ Q4: Who are the most influential authors on women entrepreneurship success?
- ❖ Q5. What are the potential future research directions of women entrepreneurship success studies?

Therefore, this article will table the current states of the research on women entrepreneurship success (WES) and view the growth of the research in this area. Hence, the objective of this paper is to present previous study trends on WES and map it with the global development of the field, and to present review literature on the overview of bibliometric analysis and previous studies on related papers of WES. The remainder of this paper is organised as follows.

First, present the methods that cover in this study. Second, the analysis and findings section that follows displays the results obtained from the documents gathered in the Scopus database. Lastly, the conclusion segment thereafter discusses the summary, limitation and recommendation for future research.

II. SAMPLE AND METHODOLOGY

Data from the Scopus bibliographic database were used to draw the research sample. Full bibliographic records, including citation and bibliographical information, funding details, abstract and keywords, and so on, were included in the exported data. The primary criteria for bibliographic unit research corresponded to scientific papers published between 1988 and 2022. The competitive nature of the Scopus bibliographic platform in comparison to other specialised databases was the major research subject of several scientific papers (Harzing & Alakangas, 2016), Wider time coverage of recorded units was emphasised as its biggest advantage (Mongeon & Paul-Hus, 2016). The following keywords have been used to search relevant articles which is related to WES such as women OR female OR gender OR “*gender equality*” OR stereotyp* AND entreprene* AND success* OR sustainab* OR performance that contained in the title of the article. This study concentrated on the titles of the articles since they indicate the relevant topic that is derived from the research subject and the study’s purpose.

According to Ahmi et al. (2020), explained in their study that the title of an article should incorporate information that is potentially used to attract readers attention, as it is the first element that readers will first observe. Based on the query, the results of the given criterion amounted to 300 scientific papers, which bibliographic data was retrieved on 25 January 2022. The most significant number of documents was written in English (291), while scientific documents in Spanish (5), Portuguese (2), French, Lithuanian and Malay were also registered. In examining the bibliometric analysis, some tools are available to examine the data such as (1) Microsoft Excel to calculate the frequencies of the published materials and to design the relevant chart and graph; (2) VOSviewer (www.vosviewer.com) to construct and visualising the bibliometric networks; and (3) Harzing’s Publish and Perish software to calculate the citations metrics and some of the other frequencies.

III. ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

The analysis of extracted scholarly works includes document and source types, published by year and annual growth, subject area, keyword analysis, geographical productivity, authorship and citation analysis. Most of the findings are reported as a frequency and percentage. Meanwhile, annual growth data is presented as a number of retrieved documents per year, including their frequency, percentage, and cumulative percentage until January 2022.

Further, driven from citation analysis and citation metrics, the top 20 cited articles in women entrepreneurship success were presented.

A. Document and Source Type

The collected data is first examined based on the document type and source type. Document type refers to the document based on its originality, such as a conference paper, article, or book chapter, whereas source type refers to the type of source document, such as a journal, conference proceedings, book series, book, or book trade publication. The conference paper listed under document type may differ from those listed under source type (Zakaria et al., 2020). A paper was given at a conference; for example will be classed as a conference paper under document type. Nonetheless, based on its publication status, the same document may be categorised as a full journal article, conference proceeding, or book chapter under source type. As summarised in Table 1, the documents published on WES spread into 8 document types.

Table 1. Document Type

Document Type	Frequency	% (N=300)
Article	233	77.67%
Book Chapter	34	11.33%
Conference Paper	15	5%
Review	8	2.67%
Book	7	2.33%
Editorial	1	0.33%
Erratum	1	0.33%
Note	1	0.33%
Total	300	100

Moreover, driven from Table1, the majority type of documents were articles represented (77.67%) of the total publication compared to others as document type as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Document by Type

Source: Authors’ own

Meanwhile, as Table 2 shows, the documents maybe classified into four different source types, of which journal represents the highest type of source with 246 documents (82%) and follows by book with 33 documents (11%), next book series with 11 documents (3.67%), and lastly

conference proceedings of 10 documents (3.33%), to the total number of the publications.

Table 2. Source Type

Source Type	Frequency	% (N=300)
Journal	246	82%
Book	33	11%
Book Series	11	3.67%
Conference	10	3.33%
Proceeding		
Total	300	100

B. Publication by Year and Annual Growth

The oldest publication covered in the Scopus database, which fulfils inclusion criteria by containing key terms in the article title, dates back to 1988. Called “Bank loan officers’ perceptions of the characteristics of men, women, and successful entrepreneurs”, this paper has been published in the Journal of Business Venturing and was categorised as scientific research, written by Buttner and Rosen (1988). With the aim of scientific production’s examination, Graph 1 presents the growing trend in the number of WES publications by year, from 2010 to 2022, representing “The rise of WES production”. The publication number exported from bibliographic data indicates that “The rise of WES production” period was significantly more fruitful. However, from 1988 to 2009, only 30 published papers were identified, while 270 articles were published from 2010 onwards. Accordingly, 90% of the total number of observed publications was published during “The rise of WES production”.

Graph 1: Number of published papers per year

Source: Authors’ own

Observing Graph 1, the most fruitful production year was 2021, with 53 published papers, followed by 2020, 2019, and 2018 with 43, 37, 32 published papers respectively, which clearly shows that the WES is attracting considerable research attention during the recent years.

C. Subject Area

This study also classifies the published documents based on the subject area, as summarised in Table 3. Overall, the distribution indicates that research on WES emerges in diverse subject areas ranging from engineering, information

“State of the Art and Trends of the Research on Women, Entrepreneurship and Success: A Bibliometric Review”

technology, healthcare, mathematics, business/management, science, and social science.

Table 3. Subject Area

Subject Area	Frequency*	% (N=300)
Agricultural and Biological Sciences	4	1.33%
Arts and Humanities	10	3.33%
Business, Management and Accounting	219	73%
Chemistry	1	0.33%
Computer Science	9	3%
Decision Sciences	14	4.67%
Earth and Planetary Sciences	3	1%
Economics, Econometrics and Finance	123	41%
Energy	17	5.67%
Engineering	8	2.67%
Environmental Science	21	7%
Mathematics	4	1.33%
Medicine	1	0.33%
Multidisciplinary	3	1%
Pharmacology, Toxicology and Pharmaceutics	3	1%
Psychology	7	2.33%
Social Sciences	99	33%
Total	300	100

*Some documents are classified in more than one subject area

Besides, As reported from Table 3, most documents are in the Business, Management and Accounting area with (73%) followed by the Economics, Econometrics and Finance area with (41%) as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Document by Subject Area
Source: Authors’ own

D. Keywords Analysis

For the purpose of keywords analysis, authors mapped the keywords supplied for each document using VOS viewer, a software tool for constructing and visualising bibliometric networks (see Figure. 3&4). Furthermore, Figure.3 presents

a network visualisation of the authors’ keywords produced by VOS viewer in which colour, circle size, font size, and thickness of connecting lines indicate the strength of the relationship amongst the keywords. As indicated by the same colour, related keywords are commonly listed together in the same cluster.

Figure 3: Network visualisation map of the author keywords

The potential future research directions of women entrepreneurship success studies can be driven from a network visualisation map. For example, the diagram suggests that women entrepreneurs, motivation, personality traits and entrepreneurial success are closely related and usually co-occur together, as the “Red Cluster”. In the same vein, it is noticeable that sustainability, empowerment, women status, sustainable development and sustainable entrepreneurship are closely related and usually co-occur together, such as “Yellow Cluster” and “Orange Cluster”.

E. Geographical Distribution of Publications

Researchers from 41 countries have contributed to the publication in the women entrepreneurship success area. All countries contribute to the productivity of publications. Graph 2 demonstrates the total publication document by the top countries, which indicates the United States is ranked first in productivity with 68 (22.67%) published documents.

Graph 2: Number of published papers per year

Source: Authors’ own

“State of the Art and Trends of the Research on Women, Entrepreneurship and Success: A Bibliometric Review”

Furthermore, Figure 4 presents a network visualisation map of the citation by countries, which indicates the United States, India, United Kingdom, and Malaysia were among the countries that received a huge number of citations in flipped WES studies.

Figure 4: Network visualisation map of the citation by countries

F. Citation Analysis

Table 4 summarises the citation metrics for the retrieved documents as of 25 January 2022. Table 4 shows the total number of citations with the average citation per year for all retrieved documents. As indicated, there are 3898 citations

reported in 34 years (1988 – 2022) for 300 retrieved articles with an average of 114 citations/year.

Meanwhile, Table 5 discloses 20 most cited articles (based on the number of cited times). In addition to total citations reported by Scopus. The document entitled “*Women’s organisational exodus to entrepreneurship: Self-reported motivations and correlates with success*” by Buttner and Moore (1997) has so far received the highest number of citations (483 citations or an average of 19 citations per year).

Table 4. Citations Metrics

Metrics	Data
Publication years	1988-2022
Citation years	34 (1988-2022)
Papers	300
Citations	3898
Citations/year	114.56
Citations/paper	12.99
Citations/author	2082.16
Papers/author	142.27
h-index	28
g-index	55

Table 5. Top 20 cited articles

No.	Authors	Title	Year	Cites	Cites per Year
1	Buttner, E. H., & Moore, D. P	Women’s organisational exodus to entrepreneurship: Self-reported motivations and correlates with success	1997	483	19.32
2	Lerner, M., Brush, C., & Hisrich, R	Israeli women entrepreneurs: An examination of factors affecting performance	1997	246	9.84
3	Shelton, L. M	Female entrepreneurs, work-family conflict, and venture performance: New insights into the work-family interface	2006	213	13.31
4	Powell, G. N., & Eddleston, K. A	Linking family-to-business enrichment and support to entrepreneurial success: Do female and male entrepreneurs experience different outcomes?	2013	202	22.44
5	Buttner, E. H., & Rosen, B	Bank loan officers’ perceptions of the characteristics of men, women, and successful entrepreneurs	1988	161	4.74
6	McElwee, G., & Al-Riyami, R	Women entrepreneurs in Oman: Some barriers to success	2003	116	6.11
7	Hughes, K. D	Exploring Motivation and Success Among Canadian Women Entrepreneurs	2006	102	6.38
8	Shaw, E., Marlow, S., Lam, W., & Carter, S.	Gender and entrepreneurial capital: Implications for firm performance	2009	69	5.31
9	Akehurst, G., Simarro, E., & Mas-Tur, A	Women entrepreneurship in small service firms: Motivations, barriers and performance	2012	68	6.8
10	Ramadani, V	The woman entrepreneur in Albania: An exploratory study on motivation, problems and success factors	2015	65	9.29

11	Hallak, R., Assaker, G., & Lee, C	Tourism Entrepreneurship Performance: The Effects of Place Identity, Self-Efficacy, and Gender	2015	55	7.86
12	Cabrera, E. M., & Mauricio, D	Factors affecting the success of women entrepreneurship: a review of literature	2017	54	10.8
13	Javadian, G., & Singh, R. P	Examining successful Iranian women entrepreneurs: An exploratory study	2012	52	5.2
14	Huang, K. H., Mas-Tur, A., & Yu, T. H. K	Factors affecting the success of women entrepreneurs	2012	51	5.1
15	Lee, I. H., & Marvel, M. R	Revisiting the entrepreneur gender-performance relationship: A firm perspective	2014	50	6.25
16	Hmieleski, K. M., & Sheppard, L. D	The Yin and Yang of entrepreneurship: Gender differences in the importance of communal and agentic characteristics for entrepreneurs subjective well-being and performance	2019	44	14.67
17	Bhardwaj, B. R	Impact of education and training on performance of women entrepreneurs: A study in emerging market context	2014	42	5.25
18	Arzubiaga, U., Iturralde, T., Maseda, A., & Kotlar, J	Entrepreneurial orientation and firm performance in family SMEs: the moderating effects of family, women, and strategic involvement in the board of directors	2018	41	10.25
19	R Bellu, R	Task role motivation and attributional style as predictors of entrepreneurial performance: female sample findings	1993	39	1.34
20	Xie, X., & Lv, J	Social networks of female tech-entrepreneurs and new venture performance: the moderating effects of entrepreneurial alertness and gender discrimination	2016	36	6

IV. CONCLUSION

Greater concern over women entrepreneurship success issues comes hand in hand with the growing awareness towards Sustainable Development Goal 5 concerns gender equality and is fifth of the 17 Sustainable. The official wording of SDG 5 is “Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls”. Thus, looking into the findings, the number of published documents regarding women entrepreneurship success significantly increased in recent years, which justifies the reasons on growing attention that attracted considerable attention from scholars worldwide to examine and recommend possible remedies to deal with issues that can hinder women from the entrepreneur’s success.

As a result, this study has evaluated all types of scientific papers published on this subject to date. The study indicated the trend of previous studies using specified bibliometric indicators derived from the Scopus database. Overall, bibliometric details of 300 documents were extracted from the Scopus database. The results indicate that English becomes a primary language in about 97% of the retrieved documents. The data also shows a growing trend in the number of WES publications by year, from 2010 to 2022, which represent “The rise of WES production”. As for the

contributing authors, the USA reported the highest numbers of contributing authors, followed by India, United Kingdom and Malaysia. Nonetheless, several European and Asian countries have made significant contributions to this research subject through scholarly works. Furthermore, issues pertaining to WES get attention from diverse subject areas such as engineering, information technology, healthcare, mathematics, business/management, science and social science. Nevertheless, 73% of examined documents are classified under business/management, science.

Despite the useful insights provided by this paper, readers should still be aware of several limitations. To begin, this paper used particular queries/keywords to discover the initial list of scholarly works published as indexed by Scopus. Nonetheless, this method was prevalent in previous bibliometrics-related studies (Ahmi et al., 2020; Zakaria et al., 2020). Although Scopus is one of the largest online databases indexing all scholarly papers, it still does not contain all sources available completely. As a result, some exclusions are to be expected from this paper. Moreover, no search query can contain all of the scholarly papers in this area fully. As a consequence, false positive and false negative outcomes are always to be expected. Scopus’ definition was used to estimate the ranking of authors in this

study. Some authors may also enrol multiple names in Scopus or have their names spelt differently. Thus, it resulted to the inaccuracy of the productivity of their authorship and affiliation details. Despite these limitations, this work presents a unique look at women's entrepreneurship studies by presenting a more comprehensive, systematic, and objective evaluation. Previous qualitative review studies have mainly relied on subjective judgement, whereas a few quantitative review studies have merely described statistical data.

The study supplements and extends on earlier reviews by conducting co-citation and co-occurrence network analyses and presenting them in a comprehensive and transparent format. moreover, quantitatively traced the evolution of women entrepreneurship research from 1988 to 2022. The study review, in fact, helps to highlight how the frontiers of the women entrepreneurship field evolve over time and give readers with a better understanding of the rapidly developing body of works in the entrepreneurship development and women entrepreneurship success area. Based on a wide sample of women entrepreneurship studies, this study combines a landscape visualisation with a timeline visualisation to provide a comprehensive overview of the women entrepreneurship literature. Moreover, for each of the main research directions, this study, in brief, this review catalyses future women entrepreneurship studies by offering scholars with a comprehension of the entrepreneurial success, hot topics and potential future trends in the female entrepreneurship domain.

REFERENCES

1. Agarwal, S., Ramadani, V., Dana, L., Agrawal, V., & Dixit, J. (2021). Assessment of the significance of factors affecting the growth of women entrepreneurs: study based on experience categorization. *Journal Of Entrepreneurship In Emerging Economies*, 14(1), 111-136. doi: 10.1108/jeee-08-2020-0313.
2. Ahmi, A., Tapa, A., & Hamzah, A. H. (2020). Mapping of Financial Technology (FinTech) Research: A Bibliometric Analysis. *International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology*, 29(8), 379-392.
3. Akehurst, G., Simarro, E., & Mas-Tur, A. (2012). Women entrepreneurship in small service firms: Motivations, barriers and performance. *The Service Industries Journal*, 32(15), 2489-2505.
4. Aparicio, S., Audretsch, D., Noguera, M., & Urbano, D. (2022). Can female entrepreneurs boost social mobility in developing countries? An institutional analysis. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 175, 121401.
5. Armuña, C., Ramos, S., Juan, J., Feijóo, C., & Arenal, A. (2020). From stand-up to start-up: exploring entrepreneurship competences and STEM women's intention. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 16(1), 69-92.
6. Arzubaga, U., Iturralde, T., Maseda, A., & Kotlar, J. (2018). Entrepreneurial orientation and firm performance in family SMEs: the moderating effects of family, women, and strategic involvement in the board of directors. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 14(1), 217-244.
7. Rauth Bhardwaj, B. (2014). Impact of education and training on performance of women entrepreneurs. *Journal Of Entrepreneurship In Emerging Economies*, 6(1), 38-52.
8. Buttner, E. H., & Moore, D. P. (1997). Women's organizational exodus to entrepreneurship: self-reported motivations and correlates with success. *Journal of small business management*, 35, 34-46.
9. Buttner, E. H., & Rosen, B. (1988). Bank loan officers' perceptions of the characteristics of men, women, and successful entrepreneurs. *Journal of Business venturing*, 3(3), 249-258.
10. Cabrera, E., & Mauricio, D. (2017). Factors affecting the success of women's entrepreneurship: a review of literature. *International Journal Of Gender And Entrepreneurship*, 9(1), 31-65. doi: 10.1108/ijge-01-2016-0001
11. Costa, J., & Pita, M. (2020). Appraising entrepreneurship in Qatar under a gender perspective. *International Journal Of Gender And Entrepreneurship*, 12(3), 233-251. doi: 10.1108/ijge-10-2019-0146.
12. Crecente, F., Sarabia, M., & del Val, M. (2021). Sustainable Entrepreneurship in the 2030 Horizon. *Sustainability*, 13(2), 909. doi: 10.3390/su13020909.
13. Elam, A. B., Brush, C. G., Greene, P. G., Baumer, B., Dean, M., Heavlow, R., & Global Entrepreneurship Research Association. (2019). Women's Entrepreneurship Report 2018/2019.
14. Gruber, J., Mendle, J., Lindquist, K. A., Schmader, T., Clark, L. A., Bliss-Moreau, E., ... & Williams, L. A. (2021). The future of women in psychological science. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 16(3), 483-516.
15. Hallak, R., Assaker, G., & Lee, C. (2015). Tourism entrepreneurship performance: The effects of place identity, self-efficacy, and gender. *Journal of Travel Research*, 54(1), 36-51.
16. Harzing, A. W., & Alakangas, S. (2016). Google Scholar, Scopus and the Web of Science: a longitudinal and cross-disciplinary comparison. *Scientometrics*, 106(2), 787-804.
17. Hassan, S., & Ahmi, A. (2022) Mapping the State of the Art of Scientific Production on Requirements Engineering Research: A Bibliometric Analysis.

- International Journal of Information Technologies and Systems Approach*, 15(1), 23.
18. Hmieleski, K. M., & Sheppard, L. D. (2019). The Yin and Yang of entrepreneurship: Gender differences in the importance of communal and agentic characteristics for entrepreneurs' subjective well-being and performance. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 34(4), 709-730.
 19. Huarng, K. H., Mas-Tur, A., & Yu, T. H. K. (2012). Factors affecting the success of women entrepreneurs. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 8(4), 487-497.
 20. Hughes, K. D. (2006). Exploring motivation and success among Canadian women entrepreneurs. *Journal of Small Business & Entrepreneurship*, 19(2), 107-120.
 21. Javadian, G., & Singh, R. P. (2012). Examining successful Iranian women entrepreneurs: an exploratory study. *Gender In Management: An International Journal*, 27(3), 148-164.
 22. Kataria, A., Kumar, S., & Pandey, N. (2021). Twenty-five years of Gender, Work and Organization: A bibliometric analysis. *Gender, Work & Organization*, 28(1), 85-118.
 23. Lee, I. H., & Marvel, M. R. (2014). Revisiting the entrepreneur gender–performance relationship: a firm perspective. *Small Business Economics*, 42(4), 769-786.
 24. Lerner, M., Brush, C., & Hisrich, R. (1997). Israeli women entrepreneurs: An examination of factors affecting performance. *Journal of business venturing*, 12(4), 315-339.
 25. Majumder, N., Pandya, M., Chaudhari, S. P., Bhatt, A., & Trivedi, D. (2021). Measuring the global research output and visualization on gender equality: a bibliometric analysis. *Library Philosophy and Practice* (e-Journal), 5803, 1-21.
 26. McElwee, G., & Al-Riyami, R. (2003). Women entrepreneurs in Oman: some barriers to success. *Career Development International*.
 27. Mongeon, P., & Paul-Hus, A. (2016). The journal coverage of Web of Science and Scopus: a comparative analysis. *Scientometrics*, 106(1), 213-228.
 28. Powell, G. N., & Eddleston, K. A. (2013). Linking family-to-business enrichment and support to entrepreneurial success: do female and male entrepreneurs experience different outcomes?. *Journal of business venturing*, 28(2), 261-280.
 29. Pritchard, A. (1969). Statistical bibliography or bibliometrics. *Journal of documentation*, 25(4), 348-349.
 30. R Bellu, R. (1993). Task role motivation and attributional style as predictors of entrepreneurial performance: Female sample findings. *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development*, 5(4), 331-334.
 31. Ramadani, V. (2015). The woman entrepreneur in Albania: an exploratory study on motivation, problems and success factors. *Journal of Balkan and Near Eastern Studies*, 17(2), 204-221.
 32. Roth, J. C. G., Hoeltz, M., & Benitez, L. B. (2020). Current approaches and trends in the production of microbial cellulases using residual lignocellulosic biomass: a bibliometric analysis of the last 10 years. *Archives of microbiology*, 1-17.
 33. Shaw, E., Marlow, S., Lam, W., & Carter, S. (2009). Gender and entrepreneurial capital: implications for firm performance. *International Journal Of Gender And Entrepreneurship*, 1(1), 25-41.
 34. Shelton, L. M. (2006). Female entrepreneurs, work–family conflict, and venture performance: New insights into the work–family interface. *Journal of small business management*, 44(2), 285-297.
 35. Slavinski, T., Todorović, M., Vukmirović, V., & Montenegro, A. M. (2020). Women, Entrepreneurship and Education: Descriptive Bibliometric Analysis Based on SCOPUS Database. *JWEE*, (3-4), 181-201.
 36. Wach, D., Stephan, U. and Gorgievski, M. (2016), “More than money: developing an integrative multi-factorial measure of entrepreneurial success”, *International Small Business Journal*, Vol. 34 No. 8, pp. 1098-1121.
 37. Xie, X., & Lv, J. (2016). Social networks of female tech entrepreneurs and new venture performance: the moderating effects of entrepreneurial alertness and gender discrimination. *International Entrepreneurship And Management Journal*, 12(4), 963-983.
 38. Zakaria, R., Ahmi, A., Ahmad, A., & Othman, Z. (2020). Worldwide melatonin research: a bibliometric analysis of the published literature between 2015 and 2019. *Chronobiology International*, 38(1), 27-37.